

all five environments. Five other hybrids—IR54754A/WGL3962, IR54754A/Vajram, IR58025A/WGL3962, IR62829A/WGL3962, and IR62829A/Swarna—were found superior in four of the five environments studied. Their performance is mainly attributable to heterosis for the number of productive tillers per plant and the number of filled grains per panicle. Only one hybrid, IR62829A/Vajram, which ranked third in grain yield, was stable over the environments with predictable performance ($b_i = 1.57$). Based on linear regression coefficients,

however, the IR58025A/Swarna hybrid with highest yield (1125 g m^{-2}) and high heterosis for yield (85.8) was found to be most suitable for specific environments. The other hybrids, IR58025A/Vajram and IR62829A/Swarna, which had above-average yield (1004 and 857 g m^{-2}) and average response ($b_i = 0.63$ and 2.06) though unpredictable for yield, may also be suitable for specific environments. All four hybrids offer greater scope for commercial exploitation of heterosis in India. ■

IR64, WGL 3962, and IR36 showed good GCA effects for test weight. The line IR54752A was found to be a good combiner for a number of characters, including longer duration and plant height. Among the six restorer lines, Vajram was ranked as a good general combiner for yield, grain number per panicle, spikelet fertility, longer duration, and plant height.

Only the following hybrids showed high SCA effects for one or more characters: IR46830A/WGL 3962 for early flowering; IR54752A/Pratibha for tallness, spikelet fertility, and grain yield; IR46830A/Pratibha for dwarf plant height; IR46830A/Vajram for productive tillers per plant; IR62829A/Pratibha for panicle length; IR46830A/IR36 for grain number; and IR62829A/Pratibha for test weight. Some of these hy-

Combining ability of rice cultivars with IRRI-bred cytoplasmic male sterile lines

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We studied the general combining ability (GCA) of 11 parents (five cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines and six restorer lines) and the specific combining ability (SCA) of 30 crosses in a 5 (line) / 6 (tester) mating design. All the 41 treatments (30 F_{1} s, 5 lines, and 6 testers) were evaluated in a completely randomized block design with three replications during the 1991-92 dry season (DS) under irrigation. Thirty plants for each entry were grown in three 1.5-m row plots with a spacing of 15×15 cm. Five competitive plants were randomly selected from each plot for analysis.

The restorer line WGL 3962 was the best general combiner for grain yield, the CMS line IR46830A was the best general combiner for number of productive tillers per plant, and IR54752A exhibited good GCA for panicle length (Table 1). Three CMS lines (IR58025A, IR62829A, and IR54752A) and three restorer lines (Vajram, IR36, and Swarna) were good combiners for filled grain number per panicle. The lines

IR54752A, IR54754A, WGL3936, Swarna, Vajram, and IR36 were found to be good combiners for spikelet fertility. The line IR54754A and testers

Table 1. General combining ability for grain yield and other characters of 11 parental lines.

Parent	Days to 50% flowering	Plant height	Productive tillers plant ⁻¹	Panicle length	Grains panicle ⁻¹	Test weight fertility	Spikelet fertility	Grain yield
<i>CMS lines</i>								
IR46830 A	-7.95**	-7.80**	1.60**	-0.49**	-24.45**	-0.56*	-9.55**	-126.1**
IR54725 A	4.86**	10.41**	-1.05**	1.03**	8.42**	0.36*	10.43**	83.9**
IR54754 A	1.69**	-0.28	-1.70**	-0.50**	-7.81**	2.57**	3.08*	-81.8**
IR58025 A	4.02**	3.58**	0.69*	0.65**	13.18**	-0.43*	-4.45**	36.0
IR62829 A	-2.98**	-5.92**	0.46*	-0.69**	10.67**	-1.95**	0.50	87.9**
S.E. GCA (L)	0.27	0.81	0.43	0.18	2.75	0.29	1.26	9.9
<i>Restorers</i>								
WGL 3962	-2.03**	-2.52**	0.46	0.27*	1.16	1.93**	5.85**	160.9**
Swarna	1.23**	-0.01	0.50*	-0.51**	7.86**	-1.75**	9.84**	51.8**
Vajram	1.03**	6.72**	1.10	-0.10	35.56**	-1.89**	8.14**	121.6**
Pratibha	3.97**	1.77*	0.04	0.77*	-26.16**	-2.05**	-21.7**	-191.8**
IR36	1.23**	-3.60**	-1.00**	-0.50**	13.91**	1.38**	7.90**	-8.2
IR64	-2.97**	-2.36**	-0.10	0.07	-32.32**	2.38**	-10.01**	-134.3**
S.E. GCA (T)	0.29	0.89	0.47	0.20	3.00	0.33	1.38	10.8

Table 2. SCA effects for grain yield and yield components of elite hybrids (showing >30% standard heterosis).

Hybrids	Standard heterosis	Days to 50% flowering	Plant height	Productive tillers plant ⁻¹	Panicle length	Grains panicle ⁻¹	Test weight	Spikelet fertility	Grain yield
IR58025 A/WGL 3962	89.5	-5.02	0.02	-0.31	0.53	17.55**	-0.72	1.59	209.0**
IR62829 A/WGL 3962	70.0	2.64	-0.35	-1.16	-0.80	-15.30**	-0.11	-3.86	34.4
IR54752 A/Pratibha	68.1	-2.19	6.77**	-0.69	0.08	24.24**	0.48	20.90**	379.2**
IR46830 A/Vajram	67.5	-2.14	3.34	3.00**	-0.42	20.52**	-0.01	13.50**	271.9**
IR62829 A/Swarna	65.5	-0.62	-3.99*	1.27	-0.55	-12.10	-0.03	-8.60**	114.6**
IR58025 A/Swarna	56.9	1.71	2.08	-0.35	0.51	-5.48	2.02	0.83	-88.5**
IR46830 A/IR36	51.3	3.12	2.56	-0.44	0.78	34.33**	0.71	17.47**	298.0**
IR54752 A/IR36	58.6	-3.32	-5.53*	-0.52	0.02	-6.10	0.88	-5.85	71.7**
IR62829 A/Vajram	48.6	-1.76	-3.65	-2.00**	3.67	3.67	0.22	-5.86	-62.8**
IR54752 A/WGL 3962	41.8	3.81	0.05	2.69**	-0.32	-15.92**	-1.11	-11.13**	-140.8**

brids are shown in Table 2, which also reports SCA effects of elite hybrids showing 30% standard heterosis.

The parental lines IR62829A and WGL 3962 had the highest GCA effects in their respective female and male groups for grain yield. Parents with high GCA values exhibited average SCA effects for longer duration in their

cross. Among the 10 crosses with positive SCA effects for grain yield, seven involved one good combiner for grain yield, and the others good, average, or poor, indicating interaction between positive and negative alleles. The cross combination showing high SCA effect for grain yield also showed high SCA effects for number of filled grains. ■

Callus induction from indica rice coleoptiles

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Rice coleoptiles have been used in tissue culture and genetic transformation, but reports on callus induction and subsequent plant regeneration from such explants in indica type varieties are scarce. We obtained significant improvements in callus induction from coleoptiles by testing different explant and culture media conditions. Mature seeds from the Perla rice cultivar were dehulled, sterilized, and the seedlings were grown on solid MS medium in the dark at 27 °C. Coleoptiles were aseptically extracted with a scalpel from 3-, 4-, 5-, or 7-d-old seedlings and incubated in N6 medium supplemented with 2 mg 2, 4-D L⁻¹ (N621, unless other-

1. Diagram showing basal and apical portions of coleoptiles.

wise stated. In the first attempt for inducing callus from both apical and basal portions from coleoptiles (Fig. 1), apical sections did not render callus regardless of their age in culture. Basal portions from coleoptiles cultivated for 3, 4, or 5 d produced significantly more calli than did those from 7-d-old coleoptiles (Fig. 2a), so in all subsequent experiments only basal portions from 3-d-old rice coleoptiles were used. Figure 1 shows results of culturing coleoptile basal portions in N62 medium with NAA. Adding 0.1 mg NAAL⁻¹ resulted in a significant increase in callus induction over N62 medium containing no NAA. Concentrations of 0.5 or 1 mg NAAL⁻¹ also improved induction as compared with the N62 medium. Effects increasing sucrose concentration were also tested. While 4.5% sucrose increased callus formation very significantly, 6% gave results lower than the control (Fig. 2b). Effects of using 2, 4-D at 3, 4, or 5 mg L⁻¹ were compared with those at 2 mg L⁻¹. Concentrations higher than 2 mg L⁻¹ improved callus induction (Fig. 2b), but no significant differences were found among 3, 4, or 5 mg L⁻¹.

Finally, four different culture media containing 2 mg 2, 4-D L⁻¹ were compared. The N6 and NMB media gave similar results and both were very significantly better than MS and AA media (Fig. 2c). Although N6 and NMB media were similar in callus induction, the NMB medium gave bigger and more embryogenic calli than those obtained with any other of the tested media or culture conditions. It also had superior results in plant regeneration frequencies. ■

% of callus induction

2. Efficiency of callus induction in indica rice coleoptiles after different tissue culture treatments. Columns marked with the same letter within a treatment are not significantly different ($p=0.01$).